

Community Intervention for Tuberculosis Active
Contact Tracing and Preventive Therapy - a cluster
randomized study
(CONTACT)

HEALTH ECONOMICS ANALYSIS PLAN
(HEAP)

VERSION 1.0 (//)

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Section 1: Administrative Information

1.1 HEAP Administrative Information

Title	Community-based Tuberculosis Tracing and Preventive Therapy (CONTACT)		
Trial registration number; registry	NCT03832023, ClinicalTrials.gov		
Source of funding	Elizabeth Glaser Pediatric AIDS Foundation/UNITAID		
Purpose of HEAP	The purpose of this HEAP is to describe the analysis and reporting procedure intended for the economic analyses to be undertaken. The analysis plan is designed to ensure that there is no conflict with the protocol and associated statistical analysis plan and it should be read in conjunction with them.		
Trial protocol version; date	This document has been written based on information contained in the trial protocol version 2.0, dated 06/02/2019		
Trial Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) version, date	SAP Version 1.0, 01/03/2019		
Trial HEAP version, date	HEAP Version 1.0, 31/01/2020		
HEAP revisions			
Roles and responsibilities	This HEAP was prepared by Dr Nyasha Mafirakureva (health economist), Dr Pete Dodd (mathematical modeller) and Prof Simon Dixon (senior health economist) and approved by the PWC*. The trial health economist(s) [Dr Nyasha Mafirakureva, Dr Pete Dodd and Prof Simon Dixon are responsible for conducting and reporting the economic evaluation in accordance with the HEAP.		
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This Health Economics Analysis Plan was developed based on a framework currently under development for health economic analysis plans in clinical trials. Thorn JC, Ridyard C, Hughes D, Wordsworth S, Mihaylova B, Noble SM and Hollingworth W (2017) 'Health economics analysis plans: the current state of play' *Trials*, **18**(Suppl 1):P144

Section 2: Trial Introduction & Background

2.1 Trial Background and Rationale

Tuberculosis remains a major public health problem in the world, with an estimated 10 million incident cases in 2017[1]. The burden of paediatric TB is substantial with the World Health Organization (WHO) estimating that, in 2017, about one million children (under 15 years) were affected by TB worldwide, and more than 250,000 children died due to this disease, including 52,000 cases of HIV-associated TB in children. Sub-Saharan Africa accounts for about one-third of all paediatric TB cases [2] with an incidence of 29-34/100,000, which is double the global average[3]. In HIV-endemic African countries, 40-60% of paediatric TB patients are also infected with HIV[4].

Children, under the age of 5 years or 5-15 years living with HIV, living in the same household with an index TB case are at an increased risk of infection and subsequent progression to active TB disease[5, 6]. Furthermore, these children are more prone to severe forms of disseminated disease, such as tuberculosis meningitis, and have a higher mortality rate than other age groups[7-9]. Tuberculosis in children is largely under-diagnosed or underreported due to non-specific symptoms and difficulties in diagnosis, as well as the historical bias towards case detection in adults[10, 11], making it hard to assess the actual burden of the childhood TB epidemic. As a result, only 39% of estimated paediatric TB cases are notified to national TB programs (NTPs), leaving a large proportion of children undiagnosed or unreported[2].

The recent shift in focus towards their diagnosis, treatment and prevention, under the strategy of “Leave no one behind”[2] may help improve the cascade of TB care in children. The availability of TB medicines in formulations that are appropriate or well tolerated by children[12], and the existence of effective preventive treatment to help ensure children exposed to TB do not develop TB disease will go a long way towards curbing the burden of paediatric TB. Identifying tuberculosis exposure and infection is an important step towards ensuring access to these treatments, and is particularly urgent in young children who are at high risk for infection once exposed, and for progression to active disease once infected. Innovative approaches that focus on integration and decentralization of paediatric TB services are required to broaden access to diagnosis, care, treatment and preventive therapy among children in need.

Several gaps in the cascade of care for TB child contacts have been documented particularly in the screening, failure to diagnose TB or complete treatment[13], preventive therapy (PT) initiation and PT completion [14]. Household or community-based contact screening is likely to improve the uptake and acceptability of child contact screening and management as well as adherence to PT and to reduce costs and workload at facility level[15, 16]. Community interventions are more developed and have had successes in HIV, malaria and Mother and Child Health (MCH) care. Evidence from community-based interventions showed better adherence to PT and higher completion rates in children [14]. Currently, no studies have evaluated the impact of interventions including both identification of children with signs suggestive of active TB disease and referral for further diagnostic work up and PT initiation and follow-up at community level on the cascade of care for children with active and latent TB, as compared to facility-based interventions. Additionally, there is limited evidence on the costs and cost-effectiveness of these approaches despite their importance in informing policy and decision-making. Our objective is to perform an economic evaluation alongside a multicentre, cluster randomized trial conducted in two TB high-burden resource-limited countries (Cameroon and Uganda) comparing tuberculosis contact tracing and intervention at community level model to

facility-based standard of care. This protocol sets out in detail, the analysis and reporting procedures intended for the economic analyses to be undertaken alongside the CONTACT trial.

2.2 Aim of the Trials

The trial aims to compare the cascade of care in two models for TB screening and management of household TB child contacts in two high TB burden and resource-limited countries, Cameroon and Uganda;

2.3 Objectives of the trials

The main objectives of the trial are to;

- compare the cascade of care for the initiation and completion of PT in child TB contacts < 5 years or children living with HIV 5-14 years using facility-based and decentralized community-based models of care.
- compare the cascade of care for the detection and treatment of TB in child contacts using facility-based and decentralized community-based models of care.

2.4 Trial population

All child household contacts of tuberculosis index cases identified who are eligible and whose parent/caregiver gives informed consent to participate will be enrolled in the prospective follow-up of the trial.

Enrolment criteria for the prospective follow-up will be:

- Household contact
 - Age
 - i. Facility-based model in Cameroon: < 5 years or HIV infected/exposed 5-14 years
 - ii. Facility-based model in Uganda and community-based model in both countries <15 years
 - Written informed consent signed by adult contacts and by parents/guardians for children contacts.
 - Written assent for children > 7 years

Exclusion criteria will be:

- If the contact is already receiving PT or TB treatment.

2.5 Intervention and comparators

2.5.1 Community-based model (the intervention)

The intervention comprises of screening of all contacts by a trained CHW/community nurse in the household using a symptom-based screening questionnaire. The CHW/community nurse will be trained to identify the key symptoms suggestive of TB and the critical symptoms that would need immediate referral to the facility. Contacts with TB suggestive symptoms will be referred to the facility for further diagnosis. In Uganda, sputum could be collected in the community if already part of the routine practice. If the child has mild symptoms that do not qualify for presumptive TB (fever or cough for less than 2 weeks), then the CHW/community nurse will come back in 2 weeks to reassess the child. The symptomatic children will be referred to the health facility for diagnosis

confirmation and treatment. HIV positive children who present with cough, fever, loss of playfulness or weight loss will be referred to the facility no matter the duration of their symptoms. The CHW/community nurse will offer HIV testing for contacts with unknown HIV result and who accept to be tested following national guidelines. For settings using CHWs, PT eligibility assessment and initiation will be done at the community level by a nurse during a follow-up visit within a week's time because the 3RH preventive therapy is not yet recommended by the NTP in Uganda and Cameroon.

At PT initiation, children will be weighed to adjust the treatment dose to the body weight and the treatment for 2 weeks will be given to the parent/guardian. Parents/guardians will be asked to report the daily dose intake on a treatment card and will be counselled on adherence and tolerability. They will be told to contact the CHW/community nurse in case of any symptoms, questions or issues that may arise in order to organize a visit by the CHW/community nurse or to refer the child to the facility for further assessment.

The CHW/community nurse will follow-up children on PT in the first week, in two weeks and then monthly until the course is completed. At each follow-up visit, the CHW/community nurse will verify the child's body weight and adjust the number of tablets if necessary and refills of the PT. Adherence to treatment will be assessed by a standardized short questionnaire and by checking the treatment card. Presence of TB symptoms will also be assessed at each visit by the CHW. The recommended monthly follow-up at the facility will be followed for children diagnosed with TB. The follow-up of the children on PT in the community-based model of care is detailed in Figure 2.

2.52 Facility-based model (the standard of care) – comparator

This model is based on the standard of care recommended by the National TB Program of each country. In Uganda, the SOC includes all age community-based contact screening but only children <5 years and HIV+ children 5-14 years are referred to the facility to initiate PT if eligible. The index will be informed that his/her household will be visited within 2 weeks for screening of contacts in the household. Current practices will be followed with prior call of the index case about the visit and extra-visit in case contacts were not present at the household during the first visit. During household visit done by the facility personnel as per national guidelines, symptomatic contacts will have sputum collected on spot if they are able to produce specimen. The child will be referred for TB treatment if specimen is smear or Xpert positive and for further investigations if still symptomatic with negative results. Symptomatic children unable to produce sputum will be referred to the facility for further diagnosis.

In Cameroon, the index case will be asked to bring his/her child contacts <5 years and HIV-infected/exposed children 5-14 years to the health facility for screening within the next 2 weeks. If children are not brought to the facility within the 2 weeks period, a maximum of 2 reminders will be sent by SMS or phone calls to the index case or parent/guardian. Screening will be done by the TB focal person of the facility who will request further investigations for diagnosis of TB including CXR and sample collection for Xpert testing according to national guidelines if the child has TB suggestive symptoms. Symptomatic children who do not fit the definition of presumptive TB will be assessed by the facility clinician and if considered as presumptive TB, will be further assessed for TB.

In both countries, contacts with a diagnosis of TB will be immediately started on treatment. Children will receive 2RHZ +E 4RH using the new dispersible FDC, or extended regimens in case of extrapulmonary TB, as recommended by the NTP. Asymptomatic children <5 years or HIV infected 5-14 years, will be assessed at facility (in both countries) for PT initiation, and if eligible, the child will be started on PT with isoniazid and rifampicin daily for 3 months. The parent/guardian and the

child will be counselled on adherence and treatment completion by the TB nurse of the facility. Parents will be informed to bring back their children to the facility for further assessment if they become symptomatic for TB or experience adverse events. HIV testing following national recommendations will be proposed for child contacts above 5 years with unknown HIV status. Children on PT will be followed-up monthly by the study nurse at facility level for PT refill and simple adherence monitoring and tolerability assessments using a standardized short questionnaire. The follow-up of the children on PT in the facility-based model of care is detailed in Figure 1.

2.6 Trial design

The CONTACT trial is a multicentre, cluster randomized trial being conducted in two TB high-burden resource-limited countries (Cameroon and Uganda) comparing tuberculosis contact tracing and management at community level model to facility-based standard of care. The two countries were purposively selected based on the high TB burden (~ 200 per 100,000 population), geographical location and representativeness of the epidemic in sub-Saharan Africa. Facilities with diagnostic and treatment capacity detecting a minimum of 50 bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB cases per year in a rural/semi-rural or semi-urban setting were selected. The facilities correspond to district hospitals in Cameroon and health centre IV or district hospitals in Uganda. The trial aims to compare the cascade of care in two models for TB screening and management of household TB child contacts in two high TB burden and resource-limited countries, Cameroon and Uganda;

- The facility-based model (the standard of care) – child contacts will be screened at facility level in Cameroon and Uganda or household level in Uganda and preventive therapy initiation, refills of PT therapy and follow-up will be done at facility level, following current practice.
- The community-based model (the intervention) – child contacts will be screened in the household by a community health worker (CHW) and preventive therapy initiation, refills of PT therapy and follow-up will be done at household level.

A total of 20 clusters across the two countries were recruited into the trial where a cluster is defined as the facility where TB cases (index cases) are diagnosed and its catchment area. Randomization will be stratified by country and done by a statistician based in the central research unit (CRU) who is blind to the clusters characteristics other than the randomization variables.

2.7 Trial start and end dates

Recruitment for the trial started in October 2019 and is due to finish in March 2021. The follow-up period for each child contact will run for 6 months.

Section 3: Economic Approach

3.1 Aims of economic evaluations

The aim of the economic evaluation is to answer the question, ‘What is the cost-effectiveness of the community-based in comparison to the facility-based model of care for TB screening and management of household TB child contacts?’

3.2 Objectives of economic evaluations

The primary objective is to estimate the long-term cost-effectiveness of community-based in comparison to facility-based model of care for TB screening and management of household TB child contacts over a lifetime horizon using economic modelling techniques. A secondary objective of the economic evaluation is to calculate the short-term cost-effectiveness of community-based in

comparison to facility-based model of care for TB screening and management of household TB child contacts over a 3-month follow-up period in a within-trial economic evaluation. A further secondary objective is to determine the proportion of patient households that have experienced coping/dissaving in relation to care-seeking, and to inform equity and societal cost analyses.

3.3 Overview of economic analysis

The within-trial economic analysis will be performed using individual patient level data from the CONTACT trial. The analytical approaches will take the form of cost-effectiveness, where, based on trial evidence, incremental cost-effectiveness (and cost-utility) ratios will be calculated by taking a ratio of the difference in the mean costs and mean effects (or utility measure).

3.4 Jurisdiction

The trial will be conducted in Cameroon and Uganda, mainly in public health facilities where health care services are primarily free of charge or highly subsidised at the point of use.

3.5 Perspectives

The primary economic analysis will be performed from the healthcare system's perspective (all direct medical and non-medical cost are included). We will also report data on the wealth quintiles of participants and their experience of coping with any costs associated with illness and care-seeking.

3.6 Time horizon

The primary economic analysis will compare the costs and health outcomes of each arm extrapolated to a lifetime horizon using a mathematical model. A secondary analysis will be conducted as a within trial analysis at the end of the follow up period for the trial with no extrapolation (all children have been followed for 6 months after enrolment).

Section 4: Economic Data Collection and Management

4.1 Statistical software use for health economic analysis

The R language for statistical computing will be used for all data analyses.

4.2 Identification of resources

Pathway of care analysis through detailed review of the protocol, field visits and discussions with trial staff involved in the planning, implementation and coordination of the study have been undertaken identify all the individual components of tuberculosis diagnosis and treatment services involved in the two models of care. The following individual components were identified: CHW household visits, days in hospital, facility (hospital or PHC) visits; sputum smear examinations; X-ray examinations; GeneXpert tests; HIV counselling and testing; overall supervision provided by EGPAF/CaP TB; drugs dispensed; visits to a TB focal person, training provided to healthcare workers, district, provincial and national programme management. Subsequently all the activities and resources used in each component are identified. These include personnel, buildings, equipment, medications and consumables. All research related costs will be identified and excluded from the analysis. The amount of time and other resources utilized by parents /guardians will be incorporated into scenario analyses to provide a broader societal perspective of the resources associated with paediatric TB.

4.3 Measurement of resource use data

Primary data on the quantities of the individual components utilized in the pathway of care for every child TB contact from the time of enrolment up to 3 months follow-up will be collected prospectively

using a CRF designed for the trial and stored in an electronic database. These include the number of visits to healthcare facilities, number of sputum smears, number of X-rays, number of Xpert tests and type and quantity of drugs. The exact number and type of resources consumed in each individual component will be measured in physical units from expenditure records or through interviews with key facility personnel. Time spent by CHWs and other staff in providing each service will be measured from the services directly using staff time sheets specifically designed for this study. For overall supervision, the number of people involved will be quantified and the proportion of their time spent on supervision identified. All equipment will be quantified and the proportion of time they are used for tuberculosis identified. For transport, the type of vehicles used and the distances travelled per year will be quantified. For facility visits, the type of staff working on the relevant departments will be quantified and the proportion of their time spent with tuberculosis patients quantified. Staff not involved in direct patient care, and the locations at which they work, will also be quantified. Non-personnel recurrent overhead expenditure will be quantified using expenditure records. Buildings will be quantified in terms of floor area. The amount of time and other resources spent by parents /guardians will be gathered retrospectively from a random sample of the study participants, via an interviewer (research assistant) administered standardized questionnaire adapted from the WHO Global TB Programme's patient costs generic survey instrument[17].

4.4 Valuation of resource use data

All resource use will be valued in monetary terms using appropriate country specific unit costs. Unit costs for the different cost components e.g health care facility visit, X-ray examination, sputum smear examination, Xpert test and medications will be based on quoted prices or on local financial data and where this is not available, WHO-CHOICE and the wider literature will be used (with price level adjustment where necessary). Unit costs for other medicines, consumables and transportation costs will be obtained from the study financial records. The unit costs for CHW household visits will be estimated using a bottom up approach. The total unit costs for each activity/visit will be the sum of the value of staff time, equipment, furniture, building space, transportation, consumables and overheads. The value of all direct service related to time will be estimated as the product of "hours of time" and "hourly wage". Information on staff salaries will be obtained from the study financial records or relevant MoH departments. Capital costs including building, equipment, furniture and vehicle costs will be calculated based on the current replacement costs and annualized at a discount rate of 3%. Both financial and economic costs will be captured, however only economic costs will be reported to capture the likely opportunity costs associated with the two models of care. All historical or retrospective costs will be adjusted for inflation using the relevant Consumer Price Indices. Unit prices will be gathered and reported in both the local currency and USD. Local currency costs will be converted to the USD currency using the relevant average exchange rates for reporting. Costs applied from other countries will be converted to their local equivalent using Purchasing Power Parity indices.

4.5 Identification of outcomes

The health outcome measure will be the Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) quantified according to the WHO and Global Burden of Disease definition, as the sum of the years of life lost due to premature mortality in the population and the years lived with disability for people living with the health condition or its consequences.

4.6 Measurement of outcomes

Data on morbidity (active TB and sequelae) and the risk of mortality will be obtained from literature. Remaining life expectancy will be estimated using each country's age and sex-specific life table estimates.

4.7 Valuations of outcomes

The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) disability weights will be applied to the patients' TB status to estimate the years lived with TB disease. Years of life lost will be estimated by summing the number of deaths at each age, multiplied by the number of years of life remaining. DALYs are obtained by summing these two metrics.

Section 5: Economic Data Analysis

5.1 Analysis population

The full analysis will include all child household contacts of tuberculosis index cases enrolled in the prospective follow-up of the trial.

5.2 Timing of analyses

The primary economic analysis will be performed when follow-up for all children is complete and the costs and health outcomes of each arm will be extrapolated beyond the trial over a lifetime horizon. A secondary analysis will be conducted as a within trial analysis at the end of the follow up period for the trial with no extrapolation (all children have been followed for 3 months after enrolment).

5.3 Discount rates for costs and benefits

Costs and outcomes in the model extrapolation will be discounted at an annual rate of 3% as recommended by WHO-CHOICE[18] and the Gates/IDSi Reference Case for Economic Evaluation[19].

5.4 Cost-effectiveness threshold(s)

The primary economic analysis will use the published country-specific mid-point estimate of the opportunity-cost-based cost-effectiveness thresholds[20, 21]. The estimated mean DALYs and costs associated with each model of care will be combined with a feasible range of values for decision makers' willingness-to-pay (λ), to obtain the distribution of net benefits at different levels of λ .

5.5 Statistical decision rule(s)

The mean differences in costs, DALYs and net benefits between the treatment groups will be estimated with associated 95% uncertainty intervals.

5.6 Analysis of resource use

Differences in the use of resources/services between the two models of care will be described but not compared statistically.

5.7 Analysis of costs

The mean total costs, health care provider costs and patient costs, stratified by relevant patient characteristics will be calculated using data for all TB child contacts in each trial arm based on an intention-to-treat principle. We will estimate the incremental mean difference in total costs between the two models of care in the trial and 95% confidence intervals. A hierarchical generalised linear mixed model (GLMM) at the individual patient level (child contacts nested within clusters and within intervention arm). The analysis will adjust for pre-specified baseline covariates at both patient (age, HIV status, ART status, socioeconomic status) and cluster level (cluster size).

5.8 Analysis of outcomes

Measures of intervention impact will be based on those reported by the trial where relevant. For cost outcomes, the statistical approach will follow those used for trial outcomes (i.e mixed-effects modelling).

5.9 Data cleaning for analysis

Data cleaning will be undertaken using literate programming techniques and the reports made public.

5.10 Missing data

Missing economic data will be explored to determine the underlying prevalence, nature and patterns of “missingness”, and if required the most appropriate imputation techniques will be used. For example, multiple imputation methods may be used if the data is missing at random (MAR). Results of any multiple imputation analyses will be compared to complete case analysis.

5.11 Analysis of cost-effectiveness

Cost and DALY data will be combined to calculate an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) and net monetary benefit (NMB) statistic from the health care provider perspective.

We will separately report on wealth quintile of affected households, and the extent of dissaving as a result of disease and care-seeking.

Contingent on data availability, an extended cost-effectiveness analysis (ECEA) will be performed by incorporating risk protection benefits and providing a breakdown of costs, risk protection benefits and health benefits by wealth asset quintile.

5.12 Sampling uncertainty

The probabilistic sensitivity analysis will be used to determine the level of uncertainty surrounding the mean outcomes by generating at least 10,000 estimates of incremental costs and benefits, by applying the model to input parameters sampled from distributions describing their uncertainty.

5.13 Subgroup analyses/Analysis of heterogeneity

Additional analyses will be performed to investigate how cost-effectiveness varies between different patient subgroups (e.g age, HIV status, socioeconomic status).

5.14 Sensitivity Analyses

Global sensitivity analysis will be used to compute sensitivity to parameters represented with distributions (either as partial rank correlation coefficients or approximate Sobol’ indices). The impact of using different perspectives will be explored by performing a secondary analysis from a societal perspective i.e. including health sector and patient costs (direct costs and indirect costs will be collected). We will also explore the impact of using the per-capita Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for each country, which the World Health Organization (WHO CHOICE) advises is a suitable willingness to pay threshold for determining whether an intervention is cost-effective. The impact of no discounting or discounting using an annual discount rate that reflects the rate for government borrowings for costs and effects in each country will be explored in an additional analysis.

Section 6: Modelling and VOI Analyses

6.1 Extrapolation or Decision analytic modelling

Decision modelling will be used to evaluate the changes in costs and health on introducing the intervention. Modelling is necessary to extrapolate from trial outcomes on case-yield and delivery of PT to project incident cases of tuberculosis averted and morbidity and mortality outcomes. Initial conceptual models will be iteratively refined in discussion with the trialists and the HEAP updated and published with the final detailed version before data becomes available.

6.2 Model type

The model will be a decision tree model representing the flow through from an index TB patient through to their outcomes and those of their household contacts. We will also develop statistical models of household contact numbers and characteristics, conditional on index case characteristics; the co-prevalence of LTBI and TB disease; and LTFU in each stage of care.

6.3 Model structure

The model will be broadly based on a previously published simple model of household contact management[22]. The decision tree will be extended to include each of the relevant steps in the care cascade (household visits, treatment initiation, completion, etc) in order to calculate associated costs and model intervention effectiveness. The model will include index case and household contact age, sex, and HIV/ART status, LTBI status, and model the natural history of progression to TB disease, TB treatment outcomes and the effectiveness of TB preventive treatment (as well as serious adverse events). If good evidence to model describe sequelae of TB disease can be found on literature review, long-term neurological or pulmonary sequelae will be included.

6.4 Treatment effect beyond the end of the trial

We will assume that the effect of PT is solely in reducing the risk of TB progression from exposure to the index case, and that it does not generate a lasting protection against TB. Similarly, treatment for active TB will not be assumed to affect long-term risks of developing TB.

6.5 Other key assumptions

The model will not be dynamic (ie accounting for indirect effects due to any reduction in TB transmission). We will assume that children under 15 are not infectious. We will use country-specific UN life-tables to estimate life-years lost. In the absence of data on LTBI prevalence in contacts participating in the CONTACT study, we will be using data from systematic reviews on LTBI prevalence in household contacts and will perform sensitivity analysis around this parameter.

6.6 Methods for identifying and estimating parameters

The majority of parameters will be characterised directly from trial or literature data. For example, parameters governing progression to disease and case-fatality will be as in previous models, i.e. based on literature reviews. We will systematically review the literature for data to support inclusion of TBM-related neurological sequelae. Parameters governing the effect of the trial in increasing linkage to care will be based on statistical models of the relevant step in the care cascade, based on trial data. Where there is evidence to support a difference between expectations based on literature and observations in the trial populations, calibration will be used to specialise parameters to the trial population. For example, prior estimates of the co-prevalence of active disease from systematic review may not apply in these settings; we will use these as priors and apply Bayesian methods to

incorporate trial data on observed co-prevalence. Parameters in models describing contact numbers will also be fitted to trial data.

6.7 Model uncertainty

All model parameters will be modelled as random variables to capture uncertainty. To quantify the impact of parameter uncertainty on model results, probabilistic sensitivity analysis will be conducted on all uncertain parameters by simultaneously sampling each parameter 10,000 times from their predefined probability distributions. The modelled incremental costs and health outcomes for each sampled parameter sets will be represented on a cost-effectiveness (CE) plane. These will also be used to construct a cost-effectiveness acceptability curve (CEAC) representing decision uncertainty surrounding cost-effectiveness. The CEAC will show the probability that each model of care for child TB contacts is cost-effective at different threshold values a decision-maker is willing to pay for a specific health benefit (1 DALY averted).

6.8 Model validation

6.9 Subgroup analyses/ Heterogeneity

The following sensitivity analyses are planned:

- If there is some evidence of additional co-prevalent adults found by the intervention from notification data, assessment of the importance of secondary transmission by considering a mean number of secondary cases for this epidemiological context based on literature.
- The proportion of household contacts in each age group with LTBI
- Inclusion of benefits and costs relating to additional HIV diagnosis and ART, if there is evidence to support an effect.

Section 7: Reporting/Publishing

7.1 Reporting standards

The CHEERS guidelines[23] will be followed when reporting the health economic evaluation, in a format appropriate to stakeholders and policy makers.

7.2 Reporting deviations from the HEAP

Any deviation from HEAP will be described and justified in the final published report and publicly posted with the HEAP on Zenodo.

Section 8: Appendices

8.1 Intervention and comparator flow diagrams

Figure 1. The flowchart of participants included in the facility-based model.

¹In Uganda information about all contacts will be collected to be consistent with national guidelines.

²In Uganda screening of all contacts will be done at community level to be consistent with national guidelines

Figure 2. The flowchart of participants included in the community-based model

8.2 Health economic collection tools

8.2.1 Staff timesheets

8.2.1.1 Time sheet for capturing staff times in the facility-based model of care for TB child contact management.

Date	Staff type (e.g nurse, clinical officer, medical doctor)	Please specify activity using attached activity codes (i.e. 1-5)	Start Time	Finish Time	<p style="text-align: center;">CODES: TB Contact Screening Activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gastric aspiration 2. Sputum induction 3. Nasopharyngeal or laryngopharyngeal aspiration 4. Fine needle aspirate 5. Pleural aspirate <p>Notes: Record the time taken to obtain the sample including patient preparation, sample collection and any documentation that may be required.</p>	
20/04/19		1	9.00	10.00		

8.2.2 TB patient costs survey instrument

As a separate file, we include a patient cost survey instrument. The primary aim of this survey is to determine the proportion of households that resort to coping/dissaving as a result of TB illness, care-seeking and preventive therapy. This is a standalone piece of research that is outside the scope of this HEAP. However, data collected with this survey will be used to inform the societal perspective CEA and support a potential ECEA, hence inclusion of the instrument as a HEAP appendix.

Community Intervention for Tuberculosis Active Contact Tracing and Preventive Therapy - a cluster randomized study (CONTACT)
 Protocol version 1.1 of July 2nd 2018

Part I. Patient information to be obtained from the CRF of the CONTACT study

Question	Answer categories (circle appropriate number or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer <i>The questions in part 1 are not part of the interview and should be pre-filled before the interview</i>
1. Date of Interview	(Day/month/year)/...../.....	
2. Interviewer Name	
3. Name of country	
4. Cluster ID	
5. Place of interview (facility name)	
6. Index case ID		
7. CONTACT ID		
8. Gender	1. Male 2. Female	
9. Age of participant:	___ years	<i>Circle appropriate number or fill answer on the answer line</i>
10. HIV status	1. Negative 2. Positive 3. Unknown	
11. Treatment registration group	Preventive Therapy 1. 3RH 2. 6H 3. Other , specify.....	
12. Start date of current Preventive Therapy	(Day/month/year)/...../.....	<i>If "Other" (answer 6), exclude from the study</i>
13. The child is currently which month of treatment?	1. Month 1, ___ weeks of phase completed 2. Month 2, ___ weeks of phase completed 3. Month 3, ___ weeks of phase completed	<i>If child has completed less than 2 weeks of the current treatment phase, exclude interview. Interview takes place after a minimum 2 weeks have been completed.</i>
14. Currency used in interview:	

Part II. Informed consent

Information Sheet

Introduction to the participant:

My name is (name). The organization I am working for, Elizabeth Glaser Pediatric AIDS Foundation (EGPAF), is interested in the costs that people face when their children are treated for tuberculosis, given medicine to prevent them from getting tuberculosis, as well as the costs faced while seeking health care before any diagnosis of tuberculosis, under the study entitled "Community Intervention for Tuberculosis Active Contact Tracing and Preventive Therapy - a cluster randomized study (CONTACT)".

You are invited to participate in this survey because you have been randomly chosen among the participants of the CONTACT study. This survey involves you answering some questions about the costs you used for the care of your child that has been in contact with a tuberculosis case. It does not involve any medical procedure and it will be over in about an hour. You will not undergo any risks by participating in this survey.

The information that you choose to share will be used for research purposes. It will be shared with other researchers for further analysis and published, but all your personal information will first be deleted in order to ensure full confidentiality. The information you give us will help us better understand the economic burden faced by people in your situation.

It is important for you to understand that your participation in this study is completely voluntary. We would be really grateful if you would agree to participate in this study, but do feel free to decline. If you decline, there will be no consequence for you and your child will receive all the care and treatment they need at the health facility as usual. If you decline to participate you will not lose any benefit that you are entitled to such as receiving care and support that is provided at the clinic.

If you decide to participate, I would like to stress that you will not receive reimbursements from the study organisers for the expenses that you report on in this interview. However, your eligibility for existing reimbursement schemes will be unaffected.

If you choose to participate in this study, you may still withdraw from the study at any stage without giving any explanation for your withdrawal. Your answers will be kept confidential. At some point I will ask you about your personal income (revenue) and the income of your household. We will NOT provide this information to any tax or welfare authorities, even after the study has been completed.

In charge of this study is the Country Principal Investigator, Dr. _____, that you can contact at the following telephone number _____ or from the central country office situated in _____. This study has been approved by the National Ethics Committee that you can contact if you have questions _____. The outcome of this study will be disseminated in an open source journal and you may request a copy from the principal investigator.

Feel free to ask me any question now or during the survey.

You will receive a copy of this Information Sheet and of the signed Consent Form

Question	Answer categories (<i>circle appropriate number or fill answer on the answer line</i>)		Action for interviewer
13. Do you have any questions?			<i>Answer participant's questions</i>
14. Do you want to participate?	Yes No, because:	1. Language not good enough 2. Time constraint 3. Not comfortable 4. Other, specify:	<i>Yes → Thank you! Go to interview No → End the interview here having filled part I from participant card</i>

Consent Form

I undersigned, Mr/Mrs _____, have been invited to participate in the Cost Survey of the study entitled “Community Intervention for Tuberculosis Active Contact Tracing and Preventive Therapy - a cluster randomized study (CONTACT)”.

I confirm that:

- I understand the information provided about this survey
- The information sheet has been clearly explained to me and I have received a copy
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and my questions have been answered
- I have understood the purpose of this survey
- The risks and benefits of this survey have been clearly explained to me
- I have understood that I am free to refuse to participate or that I can stop my participation at any time during the survey
- My consent does not discharge the research workers of their responsibilities, and I keep all my rights as they are guaranteed by the law

I freely accept to participate in this study and to answer the questions of this survey.

Participant signature _____

Researcher signature _____

Date _____

Inclusion or exclusion		
Question	Answer categories (circle appropriate number or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer
15. Decision about inclusion or exclusion	1. Included 2. Excluded	If included, skip to question 17
16. If excluded, reason for exclusion	1. No informed consent 2. Child has been on treatment for less than 2 weeks of current month" (answer in question 12)	After completing this question, the survey is completed for this participant excluded from the survey.
17. Interviewee identity	1. Parent 2. Guardian 3. Other (please specify)_____	

Checklist for which parts of the questionnaire to fill for different treatment categories					
Answer to question 10	Answer to question 12	Preventive therapy treatment category and treatment phase at time of interview (tick when filled)	part III	part IV	Supervisor check
		Children receiving preventive therapy			
1-3	1	PT interviewed in Month 1 of treatment	Filled <input type="checkbox"/>	Filled <input type="checkbox"/>	
1-3	2	PT interviewed in Month 2 of treatment	Do not fill	Filled <input type="checkbox"/>	
1-3	3	PT interviewed in Month 3 of treatment	Do not fill	Filled <input type="checkbox"/>	

Part III- Costs before the current Preventive Therapy (filled for new cases in intensive phase only)

- **New cases in intensive phase.**

Out-of-pocket expenditure, reimbursements and time loss before and during TB screening and evaluation (before start of Preventive Therapy)

Question	Instructions and actions for interviewer
18. How much money and time did you spend for each visit to a health care facility before your child(ren) was/were initiated on preventive therapy, including the visit when they were considered eligible for PT?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See table below, and ask for each item • Fill one line per visit • For all that don't apply, mark/select NA • Add more rows if more visits were made before diagnosis of TB! <p>Explanation of table headings:</p> <p>Visits: Includes outpatient visits as well as hospitalizations. Should be filled in chronological order, 1st visit=visit 1.</p> <p>Type of provider: fill in provider type according to categories in question 19 where participant sought treatment or advice.</p> <p>Travel time: Hours spent to travel to and from facility</p> <p>Time spent for visit: Fill in hours for outpatient visits and hospitalizations</p> <p>Day charge: Fees for hospital days. Only for hospitalizations linked to TB diagnosis, and <u>only to be filled if not covered by the cost items below (consultation fee, radiography etc.)</u></p> <p>Consultation fee: Other charges, not covered under day charge, including direct payment to health care staff</p> <p>Radiography and other imaging: out-of-pocket payments for imaging investigation (x-rays, CT-scan, ultrasound), TB-specific and other</p> <p>Lab test fees: out-of-pocket payments for all tests, TB specific and others</p> <p>Other procedures: out-of-pocket payments for biopsy, bronchial lavage etc. but not surgery unrelated to TB</p> <p>Medicine fees: Any medicine (TB or other) prescribed before TB was diagnosed under NTP</p> <p>Other, including nutritional supplements: any other treatments, such as nutritional supplements medically indicated</p> <p>Travel: out-of-pocket payments for travel to the facility (does not include income loss), for both participant and any household member.</p> <p>Food: out-of-pocket payments for additional food bought in relation to travelling the health care visit, and during visit or hospitalization, for both patient and any household member</p> <p>Other, including accommodation: includes out-of-pocket payments related to renting a room/bed during health care visits, and any other non-medical payments related to health care visit, for both patient and any household member</p> <p>Health insurance reimbursement: amount reimbursed to patient through medical insurance (private or social security) so far, does not include expected future reimbursement</p> <p>Out-of-pocket payments (gross): Direct payment made to health-care providers by individuals at the time of service use, i.e. excluding prepayment for health services – for example in the form of taxes or specific insurance premiums or contributions. It is calculated as the sum of direct medical (A) and direct non-medical (B) costs. If patient cannot remember the details of costs above, ask for the total out-of-pocket payments of the visit, hospitalization.</p> <p>Out-of-pocket payment (net): medical and non-medical out-of-pocket payments minus reimbursements.</p>

Visit	Type of provider (see list)	Travel time (Hours):	Time spent for visit (Hours):	Medical out-of-pocket payments, (Total per visit) (A)							Non-medical out-of-pocket payments, (Total per visit) (B)					Out-of-pocket payments (A+B) (Gross)	(C)	Out-of-pocket payments per stay (A+B-C) (Net)
				Day charges (for hospitalizations only) A1	Consultation fee A2	X-ray and other imaging A3	Lab tests A4	Other procedures A5	Medicines A6	Medical payments, total ΣA1-7	Travel B1	Food during health care visit or hospital stay B2	Accommodation B3	Nutritional supplements B4	Non-medical out-of-pocket payments (Total) ΣB1-3			
1 st																		
2 nd																		
3 rd																		
4 th																		
5 th																		
6 th																		
7 th																		
8 th																		
9 th																		
10 th																		

Enter in chronological order, using one of these provider categories for each visit. Remember to probe about informal care-seeking, for example travelling to a grocery store to buy simple cough remedies or pain relief.

1. Peripheral Health Centres
2. District Medical Centre
3. District Hospitals
4. General Hospitals
5. Regional/National Hospitals
6. NGO/charitable health centre or hospital
7. Private clinic/hospital
8. Pharmacy/ Drugstore

9. Herbalist/traditional practitioners

10. Community Health Officer

11. Other _____

Part IV. Cost during current preventive therapy (to be filled for all children receiving preventive therapy)
Unless specified, this section refers to the child's current treatment phase ONLY

Question	Answer categories (check all that apply or fill answer on the answer line)	Instructions and actions for interviewer
19. Is the child on Preventive Therapy currently hospitalized?	1. Yes 2. No	If yes, the cost data collected applies to the first row of the table question below
20. Has the child been previously hospitalized <u>during this course of TB preventive therapy</u> ?	1. Yes _____Times 2. No	1. <i>Concerns only hospitalization during preventive therapy:</i> 2. <i>Does not include hospitalization before preventive therapy started:</i> <i>If answer to both question 19 and 20 are "no", then skip to question 22.</i>
21. About how much money and time did you spend for each of these hospitalizations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See table below, and ask for each item. Fill one line per visit. <p>Explanation of table headings:</p> <p>Type of hospital: fill in provider type according to categories in question 18</p> <p>Number of days hospitalized: includes outpatient visits as well as hospitalizations. Should be filled in chronological order</p> <p>Day charges: total fees for hospital days for whole hospitalization in total. Only to be filled if not covered by the cost items below</p> <p>Consultation fee: other charges, not covered under day charge, including direct payment to health care staff</p> <p>Radiography and other imaging: any imaging investigation (x-rays, CT-scan, ultrasound), TB-specific and other</p> <p>Lab test fees: includes all tests, TB specific and others, including cost of transporting samples, if paid by patient</p> <p>Other procedures: includes biopsy, bronchial lavage, etc. but not surgery unrelated to TB</p> <p>Medicine to treat TB: fees for TB medicines only, bought inside or outside hospital</p> <p>Other medicines, including nutritional supplements: any other medicine, including nutritional supplements</p> <p>Out-of-pocket payments (gross): It is the sum of out-of-pocket medical and non-medical. If patient cannot remember the details of payments above, or has a hospital bill for all costs combined, ask for the total out-of-pocket payment for the hospitalization.</p> <p>Out-of-pocket payment (net): sum of medical and non-medical out-of-pocket payments minus reimbursements.</p> <p>Travel: out-of-pocket payment for travel to the facility (does not include income loss), for both patient and any household member.</p> <p>Food: out-of-pocket payment for food bought in relation to travelling to and during the hospitalization, patient and household member.</p> <p>Other, including accommodation: payments related to renting a room/bed during health care visits and any other non-medical expenses for patient and household member.</p> <p>Health insurance reimbursement: amount reimbursed to patient so far, does not include expected future reimbursement</p>	

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Other costs during the current preventive therapy (to be filled for all children)		
Costs for drug administration during Preventive Therapy		
Question	Answer categories (check all that apply or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer
22. On a daily basis, does the child currently take their medicines without supervision or support (self-administered) or does someone in your household supervise or support them?	1. Self-administered 2. Caregiver-supported administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who is responsible for supervision of daily intake of medicines, i.e, what is done every day.
23. If supervised/supported, how many times a week?		The maximum will be 7 times a week
24. If supervised/supported, who is providing supervision/support?	1. Parent/guardian 2. Health Care Worker 3. Community health worker/volunteer 4. Family member/Relative/HH member/Friend	
25. Was there a fee paid to the caregiver-supported administration?	1. Yes If yes, amount: _____ 2. No	
Cost of outpatient visits for medical follow-up (see the doctor or nurse, have tests, pick up drugs)		
<i>This concerns clinical check-up, follow up, and additional visits due to side effects or other TB related issues. For patients in the continuation phase, ask only how many visits since the start of the intensive phase.</i>		
Question	Answer categories (check all that apply or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer
26. Do you or a household member accompany your child(ren)'s TB PT medical follow-up visits?	1. Yes. 2. No	This should be filled if a household member accompany a child or children to TB PT follow-up visits when they see a clinician. If no, skip to question 39
27. If yes, how often do you or a household member accompany your child(ren)'s TB PT medical follow-up visits?	Every week Every 2 weeks Every month Other _____	

28. How many Preventive Therapy medical follow-up visits has the child had so far <u>during this treatment</u> (to see the doctor or nurse, have follow-up tests, etc.)?	____times	<i>This concerns clinical check-up, follow up, TPT medicines pick-up and additional visits due to side effects or other TB related issues.</i>
29. How long did the last follow-up medical outpatient visit take, including travel time and waiting time (total turnaround time)?	____hours	
30. What was the cost of transport (return) at the last follow-up medical outpatient visit, including parking, in total for the child, you and/or any accompanying household member?		<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
31. What accommodation cost did you have for the last visit, in total, for the child, you and/or any accompanying household member?		<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
32. What fees did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for <u>registration/consultation</u> ?	Registration/consultation fee.....	<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
33. What fees did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for <u>radiography and other imaging</u> ?		<i>See table above for explanations</i>
34. What fees did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for <u>tests, TB tests and others</u> ?	Fees for tests.....	<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
35. What fees did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for <u>other procedures</u> ?		<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
36. What fees did you pay at the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for non-TB <u>medicines</u> , including prescriptions for medicines bought outside the facility?	Drug fees	<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
37. What fees did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit for <u>other medicines</u> , including nutritional supplements?		<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit</i>
38. What <u>other fees</u> not listed in the previous questions did you pay during the last follow-up medical outpatient visit?	Other fees.....	<i>Cost related to the latest visit. If the interview takes place at the end of such a visit use the costs for the present visit and provide local examples</i>

Costs for nutritional/food supplements (pyridoxine)

39. Do you buy any nutritional supplements <u>outside of your regular diet</u> because of the child's Preventive Therapy, for example vitamins recommended by health care staff?	1. Yes 2. No	<i>If no, skip to question 41</i>
40. If yes, how much did you spend on these nutritional supplements in the past week approximately?		

41. Do you buy any additional food <u>outside of your regular diet</u> because of the child's Preventive Therapy, for example meat, energy drinks, or fruits as recommended by health care staff?	1. Yes 2. No	<i>If no, skip to question 43</i>
42. If yes, how much did you spend on this additional food in the past week approximately?		

Health insurance scheme		
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Question	Answer categories (<i>check all that apply or fill answer on the answer line</i>)	Action for interviewer
43. Is your child covered under any of the following health insurance types?	1. Reimbursement scheme 2. Pre-payment scheme 3. Donor 4. Family/community-based scheme 5. Private health insurance 6. Employer-based medical insurance 7. None of the above	

Social position		
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Question	Answer categories (<i>circle the most appropriate or fill answer on the answer line</i>)	Action for interviewer
44. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? If currently enrolled, highest degree received.	1. Not yet started school 2. Primary school 3. Secondary school 4. Tertiary school 5. University and higher 6. Other _____	<i>This question is for the guardian.</i>
45. What was your primary employment, or normal work, or normal other main activity before you or your children started Preventive Therapy?	1. Unemployed 2. Formal paid work 3. Informal paid work	<i>This question is for the guardian. This refers to the time before PT initiation. Name all options first</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Retired 5. Student 6. Other (specify): _____ 	
46. What is your primary employment, or normal work, or normal other main activity now?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unemployed 2. Formal paid work 3. Informal paid work 4. Retired 5. Student 6. Other (specify): _____ 	<p><i>This question is for the guardian.</i></p> <p><i>This refers to the time before PT initiation. Name all options first</i></p>
Socioeconomic status Index questions.		
47. What is your main material of the floor on your dwelling? [OBSERVATION]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earth/sand 2. Dung 3. Wood/planks 4. Palm/bamboo 5. Parquet/polished wood 6. Vinyl/asphalt strips 7. Ceramic tiles 8. cement 9. carpet 	
48. What is the main material of the external walls of your dwelling? [OBSERVATION]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No walls 2. Cane/palm/trunks 3. Dirt 4. Bamboo with mud 5. Stone with mud 6. Uncovered adobe 7. Plywood 8. Cardboard 9. Reused wood 10. Cement 11. Stone with lime/cement 12. Cement blocks 13. Covered adobe 14. Wood planks/shingles 15. Other 	
49. What is the main material of the roof of your dwelling? [OBSERVATION]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No roof 2. Thatch/palm leaf 3. Sod 	

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Rustic mat 5. Palm/bamboo 6. Wood planks 7. Cardboard 8. Metal 9. Wood 10. Calamine/cement fiber 11. Ceramic tiles 12. Cement 13. Roofing shingles 14. Other 	
50. What type of fuel does your household mainly use?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Electricity 2. LPG 3. natural gas 4. biogas 5. kerosene 6. coal/lignite 7. charcoal 8. wood 9. straw/shrubs/grass 10. agricultural crop 11. animal dung 12. no food cooked in household 13. Other 	
51. What is the main source of drinking water for members of your household?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. piped into dwelling 2. piped into yard/plot 3. public tap/standpipe 4. tube well or borehole 5. protected well 6. unprotected well 7. protected spring 8. unprotected spring 9. rainwater 10. tanker truck 11. cart with small tank 	

	12. surface water (river/dam/lake/pond/stream/canal /irrigation channel) 13. bottled water 14. other	
52. What kind of toilet facility do members of your household usually use?	1. Flush to piped sewer system 2. Flush to septic tank 3. Flush to pit latrine 4. Flush to somewhere else 5. Flush, don't know where 6. Ventilated improved pit latrine 7. Pit latrine with slab 8. Pit latrine without slab/open pit 9. Composting toilet 10. Bucket toilet 11. Hanging toilet/hanging latrine 12. No facility/bush/field 13. Other	
53. Does your household have?	1. Electricity 1. Yes 2. No 2. Television 1. Yes 2. No 3. Mobile phone 1. Yes 2. No 4. Landline phone 1. Yes 2. No 5. Refrigerator 1. Yes 2. No 6. Fan 1. Yes 2. No 7. Cupboard 1. Yes 2. No 8. DVD player 1. Yes 2. No 9. Radio 1. Yes 2. No 10. Computer 1. Yes 2. No 11. Car/truck 1. Yes 2. No	
54. Does any member of your household have a bank account?	1. Yes 2. No	
55. Do you own or rent your dwelling?	1. Own 2. Rent	

Income (reported) before initiation of preventive therapy

56. Are you the person mainly responsible for taking care of the child or children on Preventive Therapy?	1. Yes 2. No	<i>If No please skip to Question 60</i>
57. Were you the person who earned the highest income in your household before anyone in your household contracted TB?	1. Yes 2. No	<i>This question is for the guardian.</i>
58. How many hours a week were you working before TB in your household?	_____ hours	<i>This question is for the guardian. This refers to the time before TB symptoms developed.</i>
59. If you were in paid work, how much do you estimate your net income from labour related activities, per month was <u>before TB in your household</u> ?	_____	<i>This question is for the guardian. For seasonal workers who experience fluctuating wages, try to ascertain an average monthly income for this question.</i>
60. How much do you estimate the net income from labour related activities of <u>your household</u> was per month, <u>before TB in your household</u> ? (All family member's income must be counted)	_____	<i>Refers to all persons in the household. For seasonal workers who experience fluctuating wages, try to ascertain an average monthly income for this question.</i>

Income changes and social consequences

Question	Answer categories (circle the most appropriate or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer <i>These questions concern the guardian</i>
61. If you are in paid work, how much do you estimate net income from labour related activities, per month is now?		<i>This question is for the guardian (ONLY ask if answer to question 60 is YES). In setting with an important informal sector you may not want to explicitly refer to taxes to make sure people are giving the right answer.</i>
62. How much do you estimate the net income from labour related activities of <u>your household</u> was per month, <u>at the time of preventive therapy initiation in your household</u> ?		<i>Refers to all persons in the household. For seasonal workers who experience fluctuating wages, try to ascertain an average monthly income for this question.</i>
63. How much do you estimate the net income from labour related activities of your household is per month <u>now</u> ?		<i>Refers to all persons in the household For seasonal workers who experience fluctuating wages, try to ascertain an average monthly income for this question.</i>
64. How many hours per week are you working now?		<i>This question is for the guardian. (ONLY ask if answer to question 60 is YES).</i>

65. Approximately how many working days of income have you lost due to preventive therapy overall?		<i>Working days of income: e.g., if a participant was not able to work for 5 half days and lost income for these, the number of days lost is 0.5*5=2.5. Report for total TB episode, incl. all days before and after job loss. This includes caring for children. (ONLY ask if answer to question 60 is YES).</i>
66. Did you or your household receive any social welfare payment after the first household preventive therapy initiation? If yes, what type and amount during the last month?	0. No 1. Option 1 ___per month 2. Option 2 ___per month 3. Option 3 ___per month 4. Option 4 ___per month	<i>This question is for the guardian. Categories according to the following categories 1. Paid sick leave 2. Cash transfer for the vulnerable (specify, elderly, OVC,MDR, disability,) 3. Nutritional Support 4. Others (specify) In setting with an important informal sector you may not want to explicitly refer to taxes to make sure people are giving the right answer.</i>
67. Do you currently receive vouchers or goods in kind to cope with preventive therapy?	1. Yes a. Travel voucher: ___per month b. Food support: ___per month c. Other, enablers etc ___per month 2. No	<i>This question is for the guardian. More than one category allowed. If no, skip to question 69</i>
68. From whom do you receive the voucher/ goods	1. Government 2. NGO 3. Employer 4. Private donation 5. Other, specify	<i>This question is for the guardian. More than one answer allowed</i>
69. How many adults and children regularly sleep in your house? (including patient, if variable, at time of diagnosis)		
70. How many rooms are there in the house excluding the bathroom?		
71. Has the preventive therapy affected your social or private life in any way?	1. No 2. Food insecurity 3. Divorce or Separated from spouse/partner 4. Loss of Job 5. Interrupted schooling	<i>More than one category allowed.</i>

	6. Social exclusion 7. Days of work lost 8. Other _____	
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Coping		
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Question	Answer categories (circle the most appropriate or fill answer on the answer line)	Action for interviewer <i>These questions are for the guardian.</i>
72. Did you borrow or receive any money to cover costs incurred since you or your child(ren) started preventive therapy?	1. Yes 2.No	<i>If No, go to question 76</i>
73. If yes, how much did you borrow/receive (in total)?	_____	
74. From whom did you borrow/receive?	1. Family 2. Neighbors/friends 3. Private bank 4. Cooperative 5. Employer 6. "Unofficial lender" (Black market) 7. Personal savings 8. Other _____	<i>Multiple responses allowed.</i>
75. Are you expected to pay the amount back?	1. Yes 2.No	
76. Have you sold any of your property to finance the cost incurred during preventive therapy?	1. Yes 2.No	<i>If no, skip to question 79</i>
77. If yes, what did you sell?	1. Land 2. Livestock 3. Transport/vehicle 4. Household item 5. Farm produce 6. Gold/jewelry 7. Other	<i>Multiple responses allowed. Circle all that are mentioned</i>
78. How much money did you receive from the sale of all items of your property (in total)?		

79. The impact on your household financially since you or your child(ren) initiated preventive therapy has been that your household became:	1 = Richer 2 = Unchanged 3 = Poorer 4 = Much poorer	
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Thank you for your cooperation! Is there anything you would like to ask or say?

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Comments by Interviewer:

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Date (dd/mm/yyyy):/...../.....	Signature interviewer:
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References

1. World Health Organization, *Global tuberculosis report 2018*. 2018: World Health Organization.
2. World Health Organization, *Global tuberculosis report 2017*. 2017, Geneva.
3. Seddon, J.A. and D. Shingadia, *Epidemiology and disease burden of tuberculosis in children: a global perspective*. J Infection Drug Resistance, 2014. **7**: p. 153.
4. Jeena, P., et al., *Impact of HIV-1 co-infection on presentation and hospital-related mortality in children with culture proven pulmonary tuberculosis in Durban, South Africa*. The International Journal of Tuberculosis Lung Disease, 2002. **6**(8): p. 672-678.
5. Dodd, P.J., et al., *Burden of childhood tuberculosis in 22 high-burden countries: a mathematical modelling study*. The lancet global health, 2014. **2**(8): p. e453-e459.
6. Fox, G.J., et al., *Contact investigation for tuberculosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. Marks. Eur Respir J, 2015. **46**: p. 578 citation_lastpage= 578.
7. Muñoz-Sellart, M., et al., *Treatment outcome in children with tuberculosis in southern Ethiopia*. Scandinavian journal of infectious diseases, 2009. **41**(6-7): p. 450-455.
8. Marais, B., et al., *The natural history of childhood intra-thoracic tuberculosis: A critical review of literature from the pre-chemotherapy era [state of the art]*. The International Journal of Tuberculosis Lung Disease, 2004. **8**(4): p. 392-402.
9. Jenkins, H.E., et al., *Mortality in children diagnosed with tuberculosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. The Lancet Infectious Diseases, 2017. **17**(3): p. 285-295.
10. Newton, S.M., et al., *Paediatric tuberculosis*. The Lancet infectious diseases, 2008. **8**(8): p. 498-510.
11. Brigden, G., et al., *Getting it right for children: improving tuberculosis treatment access and new treatment options*. Expert review of anti-infective therapy, 2015. **13**(4): p. 451-461.
12. Euro Health Group, *Global Alliance for TB drug development (TB Alliance) Speeding Treatments to End Paediatric Tuberculosis (STEP – TB) End of Project Evaluation 2017*.
13. Mwangwa, F., et al., *Gaps in the child tuberculosis care cascade in 32 rural communities in Uganda and Kenya*. Journal of Clinical Tuberculosis and Other Mycobacterial Diseases, 2017. **9**: p. 24-29.
14. Szkwarko, D., et al., *Child contact management in high tuberculosis burden countries: A mixed-methods systematic review*. PLoS One, 2017. **12**(8): p. e0182185.
15. Graham, S.M., *The management of infection with Mycobacterium tuberculosis in young children post-2015: an opportunity to close the policy-practice gap*. Expert review of respiratory medicine, 2017. **11**(1): p. 41-49.
16. Egere, U., et al., *Isoniazid preventive treatment among child contacts of adults with smear-positive tuberculosis in The Gambia*. Public Health Action, 2016. **6**(4): p. 226-231.
17. Organization, W.H., *Tuberculosis patient cost surveys: a handbook*. 2017.
18. World Health Organization, *Choosing interventions that are cost effective (WHO-CHOICE)*. 2010.
19. Claxton, K., et al., *The gates reference case for economic evaluation*. 2014: Seattle, WA, USA. The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.
20. Woods, B., et al., *Country-Level Cost-Effectiveness Thresholds: Initial Estimates and the Need for Further Research*. Value Health, 2016. **19**(8): p. 929-935.
21. Ochalek, J., J. Lomas, and K. Claxton, *Estimating health opportunity costs in low-income and middle-income countries: a novel approach and evidence from cross-country data*. BMJ Glob Health, 2018. **3**(6): p. e000964.
22. Dodd, P.J., et al., *Potential effect of household contact management on childhood tuberculosis: a mathematical modelling study*. Lancet Glob Health, 2018. **6**(12): p. e1329-e1338.
23. Husereau, D., et al., *Consolidated Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards (CHEERS) statement*. Int J Technol Assess Health Care, 2013. **29**(2): p. 117-22.